

Experimental

All the chemicals employed are of analytical grade. Spectrophotometric measurements were made with Elico Spectrocol model CL-23 (India) and pH measurements with Elico Digital pH Meter model LI-120. The reagent solution was prepared in 1,4-dioxane. All the other solutions were prepared in double distilled water.

Absorbance of the reagent and the reaction mixture consisting of uranyl ion and the reagent is measured in the pH range 1-4.5 in the wavelength range 400 nm to 650 nm. The absorbance difference for the reaction mixture (metal ion+excess reagent) and the reagent was maximum at 425 nm. Hence further studies were carried out at this wavelength.

Effect of pH :

To the buffered solution (pH 1.3 to 4.5) metal solution and the reagent solution were added so that the overall concentration of each component is $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. The absorbance for each reaction mixture is measured against the buffer solution as the blank. The absorbance of the mixture increased while that of the reagent decreased with increase in pH. However, at pH's higher than 2.5 the solution became turbid slowly and hence further studies are restricted to pH 1.3.

Obedience of Beer's law :

The absorbance of the reaction mixture varied linearly with the concentration of uranium in presence of excess of reagent. This shows that small amounts of uranium can be estimated colorimetrically with the reagent.

Composition and Stability constant :

Slope ratio method and Job's method indicated that the composition of the complex is 1 : 1. The stability of the complex is calculated from the data obtained in the Job's method and is 1.9×10^3 .

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References

1. W. O. FOYE and W. E. LANGE, *J. Am. Pharm. Assoc.*, 1955, **44**, 261.
2. G. ZAHN and EISENBRANDT, *Pharmazie*, 1964, **19**, 407.
3. J. K. AGARWAL *et al*, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1975, **82**, 65.

Quantitative Separation of Co^{++} or Cd^{++} or Cu^{++} from Ca^{++} and PO_4^{3-} and Their Complexometric Determination

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THE need for a rapid and quantitative separation and estimation of Co^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} ; Cd^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} and Cu^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} was felt during the investigation of these cation exchange reactions in Hydroxyapatite, the prototype of the inorganic constituent of bones and teeth. The present communication has been an attempt to arrive at optimum conditions for such separation and to investigate the suitability of the complexometric titration for their subsequent quantitative determination.

Procedure : To a convenient volume of a weakly acidic (HCl) synthetic solution of Ca^{2+} , Co^{2+}/Cd^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} ions, 5% solution of sodium citrate was added followed by a slight excess of 7%, NH_4CNS solution (for Co^{2+} till the solution was blue), heated just to boiling and to the hot solution 2 ml of pyridine was added. It was shaken well for 5 min and the crystalline precipitates of Co^{2+}/Cd^{2+} was allowed to settle to room temperature, filtered and the precipitate was washed thoroughly with a solution containing 1% pyridine and 1% NH_4CNS . It was then dissolved in minimum volume of 0.6M warm HCl. The solution thus containing Co^{2+}/Cd^{2+} is made up to a known volume, to a convenient aliquot of this solution 0.1 M NaOH was added to just neutral (methyl red indicator for Cd^{2+} and appearance of a slight blue precipitate for Co^{2+}).

In case of Co^{++} the solution after neutralisation was diluted to 100 ml, 5 ml of 5% NaAc was added followed by Murexide indicator. Buffer (NH_4Cl/NH_4OH) pH ~ 10 was added till the solution was yellow. The Co^{2+} was then determined by titrating against 0.01M E. D. T. A. till a sharp colour change from orange to pure pink was obtained.

In case of Cd^{2+} , to the solution after neutralisation 5 ml of buffer pH ~ 10 was added followed by 3 drops of Eriochrome Black T indicator and titrated against 0.01 M E.D.T.A. till a sharp colour change from wine red to pure blue resulted. For the Cu^{2+} , Ca^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} system the Cu^{++} in a convenient volume of the solution was precipitated by the addition of a solution containing 32% pyridine and 22% salicylic acid. The precipitate was filtered washed with a solution containing 5% solution of the precipitating reagent. It was dissolved in 0.6M warm HCl. To a known volume of this solution 0.1 M

TABLE 1—ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COPPER AND PHOSPHATE

Mix No.	Calcium in mg.		Wt% error	Copper in mg.		Wt% error	Phosphorus in mg.		Wt% error
	Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.	
I	4.018	4.020	0.049	5.893	5.893	0.00	9.500	9.500	0.00
II	19.640	19.635	0.025	32.087	32.125	0.118	47.500	47.500	0.00
III	10.020	10.025	0.049	15.888	15.899	0.088	23.750	23.780	0.12

TABLE 2—ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, CADMIUM AND PHOSPHATE

Mix No.	Calcium in mg.		Wt% error	Cadmium in mg.		Wt% error	Phosphate in mg.		Wt% error
	Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.	
I	40.24	40.22	0.049	11.24	11.232	0.0712	95.94	95.90	0.0417
II	100.20	100.25	0.049	33.72	33.7015	0.0549	47.500	47.500	0.00
III	19.640	19.640	0.00	112.40	112.395	0.0045	9.554	9.554	0.00

TABLE 3—ANALYSES OF CALCIUM, COBALT AND PHOSPHATE

Mix No.	Calcium in mg.		Wt% error	Cobalt in mg.		Wt% error	Phosphate in mg.		Wt% error
	Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.		Expt.	Theo.	
I	4.018	4.020	0.049	5.893	5.893	0.00	9.500	9.500	0.00
II	100.20	100.22	0.019	17.679	17.678	0.005	47.500	47.500	0.00
III	19.640	19.648	0.041	88.495	88.495	0.001	23.750	23.761	0.046

NaOH was added till neutral followed by 5 ml of buffer pH~10. It was diluted to 100 ml and titrated against 0.01 M E.D.T.A. using Murexide indicator till a sharp colour change from greenish yellow to deep violet is obtained.

In another set (same for the three systems) from a same amount of the aliquot solution phosphate was precipitated as phosphomolybdate¹, filtered, dissolved in minimum volume of 0.1 M hot NaOH. The phosphate was reprecipitated as magnesium ammonium phosphate, separated by filtration, washed with 20% NH₄OH, dissolved in 0.6 M warm HCl and subsequently determined complexometrically².

In all the cases the filtrate after removal of phosphate as phosphomolybdate was made up to a convenient volume and estimated for the combined cations complexometrically. For the total Ca²⁺ and Cd²⁺, the procedure adopted was similar for Cd²⁺ as mentioned above except with an additional use of Mg-EDTA complexonate before titration. For the total Ca²⁺-Cu²⁺ and Ca²⁺-Co²⁺ ions the free acid was neutralised with 0.2 M NaOH and the complexometric procedure adopted was similar with copper and cobalt determinations respectively. The difference of E.D.T.A. consumed for the total cations and the individual titre values resulted in the amount of Ca⁺⁺ present in a given mixture.

The results of chemical analyses of different representative synthetic combination are given in Tables 1-3.

The method is rapid and accurated and can be used for those metal ions which form a solid pyridine-thiocyanate or pyridine-salicylic acid complex.

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References

1. N. S. CHICKERUR and T. S. B. NARASARAJU, *Analyst*, 1968, **93**, 344; cf. *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1969, **244**, 324.
2. S. V. CHIRANJEEVI RAO and N. S. CHICKERUR, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1972, **258**, 367.

Determination of Dissociation Constants of Some Amino Acids. Part I. Use of Wet Volume Ratio Method

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APLICATION of the ion exchangers of low cross linking as analytical tools is found in the determination of water content of organic solvents and solutions, studies in valencies of various ions

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